

USE “SIX HATS” METHOD TO TEACH STUDENTS TO THINK IN THE PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article discusses the use of effective methods in teaching students to think in the educational process. Edward de Bono's Six Different Ways of Thinking to Develop Students' Critical, Creative, and Logical Thinking Skills The results of the first application of the Six Hats method in primary education are described.

Keyword. Thinking ability, critical thinking, creative thinking, logical thinking, the “six hats” method, analytical relationships.

The Indian philosopher Swami Vivekananda once said, "Education is the manifestation of human perfection." Education should contribute to the full development of the mind of every mind and body, the sensitivity of aesthetic sensibility, personal responsibility and spiritual values should allow all human beginnings to develop independent, creative and critical thinking. From Eastern culture and history to the present day, education is seen as a process of restoring power. The education system needs to be classified to solve problems in society. One of the main tasks of the education system is to develop the creative thinking skills of our children. Every child has the potential to be creative, to the fullest. It is often said that we should try to give the child the opportunity to develop creative thinking. This is important because the evolving environment, creativity, innovative skills and management skills play a big role in addressing the world’s opportunities. At the same time, we must ensure that the values enshrined in our Constitution, which have long been known in our society, develop properly. It is the preparation of the socio-economic situation and the key to the education system in the context

of the growing importance of creativity is necessary to study the concept, approach and methodology with an open mind.

At the same time as education reform is taking place, a number of changes have taken place in the primary education system in Uzbekistan, which is the first stage of the educational process. Modern textbooks have been created in a new spirit, in a new interpretation. Interestingly, for the first time, an international expert was attached to the textbook. The main goal of Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy (for students in grades 1-2) is to stimulate creative, logical, and critical thinking in the child. From the experience of developed countries, it can be seen that the disciplines of critical thinking and creative thinking are introduced to students, which teach children to develop the ability to express their thoughts and attitudes to situations and consequences, events.

Thinking skills are an increasingly important element of primary education, but teaching them can often be difficult for primary school teachers.

Thinking goes beyond memorization and encourages students to connect points between concepts, solve problems, think creatively, and apply knowledge in new ways. Despite myths that critical thinking skills apply only to sciences such as science and mathematics, and creative thinking only to literary sciences, the truth is that these skills, based on the evaluation and application of knowledge, are necessary for success not only in all disciplines but also in everyday life. .

From critical and creative thinking to how to incorporate it into everyday lessons, we'll look at six different ways of thinking by Edward de Bono, the Six Hats method, which improves the basic aspects of the fundamental intellectual skills we offer. The thing is, in English, a hat is usually a type of activity - a conductor's hat, a police hat, a chef's hat, and so on. The phrase "wearing someone else's hat" means engaging in specific activities. One wears a hat of a certain color and chooses the type of thinking associated with it.

White hat thinking is a mode of focusing on all the information we have: facts and figures. It is also important for us to "wear a white hat" to focus on the "white hat"

we have, to pay attention to additional information, and to think about where to get it.

A red hat is a hat of emotions and intuition. Without going into details and feedback, all intuitive assumptions are made at this stage. People share emotions (fear, anger, joy, etc.) that come from thinking about a particular decision or offer.

Yellow hat Positive. Wearing it, we think about the expected benefits that will make a decision or make a proposal, we think about the benefits and prospects of a particular idea. And even if this idea or decision at a glance doesn't promise any good, it's important to develop that optimistic side, the optimistic side, and try to identify hidden positive resources.

Opposite the black hat. This hat should criticize the situation (ideas, solutions, etc.): it is necessary to consider the possible dangers and hidden threats, serious and imaginary shortcomings.

Green Hat - A hat for creativity and creativity, look for alternatives and make changes. Look at all the differences, come up with new ideas, change the existing ones and follow someone else's training, don't break non-standard and provocative approaches, look for any alternative.

Blue Hat - The Sixth Thinking Hat, unlike the other five, is designed to control the problem-solving process to implement an idea and solve a problem and explore its content. In particular, to determine how the use of blue hats should be done before doing all the rest, i.e. to formulate Goals and finally to increase and discuss the advantages and effectiveness of the 6 hat method.

We first used this method among university students. In this case, we have selected Said Ahmad's "Karakoz Majnun". Students should be familiar with the work before using this method. The teacher assigns the task to read the work the day before or until the next lesson. Turns to the course process to analyze their feedback. After wearing special hats, each student thinks according to the color of the hats. A student wearing a white hat gives information and digital facts about the work, while

a student in a yellow hat describes the positive images and events in the work. It is done in this order.

This method has shown that the stages of thinking among students are effectively organized. The students looked at this method with great interest.

We used this method in our 4th graders' Reading Lessons on "An Unskilled Man Closer to Death" and "Colorful Snows." The interest in the method has been aroused since we introduced them to the chief chemists of six different colors. The student, wearing a white hat, told about the genre of the fairy tale, the author of the fairy tale and the characters involved in the fairy tale. The student wearing the yellow hat spoke about the positive aspects of the work, while the student in the black hat gave a critical attitude to the images and events in the work. The student, wearing a red hat, shared his emotional experiences as he read. The student in the green hat commented on what new ideas or alterations he might have made to the work. Wearing a blue hat, the student described the findings and solutions of the work. It has been shown that it is advisable to use this method in primary education. In today's world of globalization, everyone who develops in society is required to have

creative, free critical and analytical thinking skills. This issue is relevant and it is advisable to approach the education process responsibly.

References

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" in the new edition URQ-637. T. : <https://lex.uz/docs/-5013007>.
2. I.Azimova, K.Mavlonova, S.Quronov, Sh.Tursun "Ona tili va o‘qish savodxonligi" Part 1 1st grade textbook. Tashkent - 2021. Republican Education Center.
3. I.Azimova, K.Mavlonova, S.Quronov, Sh.Tursun "Ona tili va o‘qish savodxonligi" Part 1 2nd grade textbook. Tashkent - 2021. Republican Education Center.
4. S.Matchanov “O‘qish kitobi” 4th grade textbook. Tashkent – 2017. “Yangiyul poligraf servis”.
5. S.Ahmad “Qorako‘z Majnun” Tashkent – 2013. “O‘zbekiston”